

A. Definition of all Parameters of the Final Dataset

Table 1: Definition of all Parameters of the Final Dataset

Parameter	Description	Value Range
id	The unique tweet id of the comment.	
text	The text of the comment.	
tweet_id	The id of the original tweet to which the comment belongs.	
title	The headline of the article which is referenced by the original tweet.	
outlet	The news outlet which published the article and posted the original tweet.	
twitter_handle	The Twitter user name of the news outlet	
article_url	The URL of the article which is referenced by the original tweet.	
Ad Fontes_url	The URL to the outlet's subpage on Ad Fontes media's website.	
bias_score	The bias score of the article which is referenced by the original tweet. This score indicates the political bias. A score of 0 indicates no bias.	[-42, 42]
reliability_score	The reliability score of the article which is referenced by the original tweet. This score indicates the truthfulness.	[0, 64]
pos_score_hate	The positive hate score of the tweet returned by the XLNet-based classifier. The closer the value to 1, the higher the likelihood that the respective tweet is hate.	[0, 1]
neg_score_hate	The negative hate score of the tweet returned by the XLNet-based classifier. The closer the value to 1, the higher the likelihood that the respective tweet is non-hate.	[0, 1]
hate_value	The label indicating whether the tweet is hate or non-hate.	(non-hate, hate)
pos_score_sentiment	The positive sentiment score of the tweet returned by the XLNet-based classifier. The closer the value to 1, the higher the likelihood that the respective tweet is positive.	[0, 1]
neg_score_sentiment	The negative sentiment score of the tweet returned by the XLNet-based classifier. The closer the value to 1, the higher the likelihood that the respective tweet is negative.	[0, 1]
sentiment	The label indicating whether the tweet is positive or negative	(negative, positive)
INSULT	The score for the Perspective API attribute Insult*	[0, 1]
LIKELY_TO_REJECT	The score for the Perspective API attribute Likely to Reject*	[0, 1]
IDENTITY_ATTACK	The score for the Perspective API attribute Identity Attack*	[0, 1]
SEVERE_TOXICITY	The score for the Perspective API attribute Severe Toxicity*	[0, 1]
THREAT	The score for the Perspective API attribute Threat*	[0, 1]
FLIRTATION	The score for the Perspective API attribute Flirtation*	[0, 1]
TOXICITY	The score for the Perspective API attribute Toxicity*	[0, 1]

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Table 1: Definition of all Parameters of the Final Dataset (cont.)

Parameter	Description	Value Range
ATTACK_ON_COMMENTER	The score for the Perspective API attribute Attack on Commenter*	[0, 1]
SEXUALLY_EXPLICIT	The score for the Perspective API attribute Sexually Explicit*	[0, 1]
SPAM	The score for the Perspective API attribute Spam*	[0, 1]
INCOHERENT	The score for the Perspective API attribute Incoherent*	[0, 1]
UNSUBSTANTIAL	The score for the Perspective API attribute Unsubstantial*	[0, 1]
ATTACK_ON_AUTHOR	The score for the Perspective API attribute Attack on Author*	[0, 1]
PROFANITY	The score for the Perspective API attribute Profanity*	[0, 1]
INFLAMMATORY	The score for the Perspective API attribute Inflammatory*	[0, 1]
OBSCENE	The score for the Perspective API attribute Obscene*	[0, 1]
bias_class	The bias class of the outlet.	**
reliability_class	The reliability class of the outlet.	***
overall_reliability	The overall reliability score of the outlet.	[0, 64]
overall_bias	The overall bias score of the outlet	[-42, 42]
polarity_strength	The polarity strength of the tweet. The closer the value to 1, the stronger the polarity of the tweet (positive or negative).	[0, 1]

Note: This Table provides an explanation for all attributes of the final dataset.

* The bias classes for outlets are: 1) most extreme left, 2) hyper-partisan left, 3) skews left, 4) middle or balanced bias, 5) skews right, 6) hyper-partisan right, 7) most extreme right

** The reliability classes for outlets are: 1) original fact reporting, 2) fact reporting, 3) complex analysis or mix of fact reporting and analysis, 4) analysis or high variation in reliability, 5) opinion or high variation in reliability, 6) selective or incomplete story/unfair persuasion/propaganda, 7) contains misleading information, 8) contains inaccurate/fabricated information